

Supercharging blockchain adoption

Jan Sammut^a

^a *CEO, RefToken, The world's first decentralized affiliate platform, Malta*

Keywords:

1. Introduction

A realistic assessment of the challenges facing blockchain and decentralized startups competing with their centralized competitors, as well as potential solutions to the problem.

2. Aim

To evaluate the competitive landscape the thousands of distributed applications currently undergoing ICOs will compete in.

3. Material and methods

Market data, primary and secondary analysis as well as first-hand experience garnered from 10 years in the field

4. Results

N/A

5. Conclusions

If blockchain startups are really going to disrupt their respective sectors, they are going to require a new approach to user growth and product development

6. Keywords

Blockchain adoption, marketing, ICO, distributed applications

Author biography

Jan Sammut Jan Sammut is the founder and CEO of RefToken, the worlds first decentralised affiliate platform, as well as ICOMalta, a full stack ICO hosting provider. A marketer by profession, he has previously held executive positions at industry heavyweights such as IGT plc, Stars Group and Highlight Media Group

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